

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Moderating effect of clothing insulation on the relationship between physiological parameters of the elderly people and environmental temperature

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404529

Yu Jiao¹, Hang Yu^{1*}, Yifan Yu², Xiangyang Chu¹, Yuhua Zhu³

¹School of Mechanical Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China

²College of Architecture and Urban planning, Tongji University, Shanghai, China

³College of Civil Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China

*Corresponding author: tjyuhang@163.com

Introduction

Results from some studies indicated the importance of reasonable clothing on physiological parameters (Gagge et al.,1938; Donaldson et al.,2001; Havenith et al.,2002; Li et al.,2009; Marszałek et al.,2018) Studies have also found that the predominant strategy of thermal adaptation for elderly individuals is clothing adjustment (Cena et al.,1986; Hwang and Chen, 2010). But at the same time, it was found that because of the low level of activity of the elderly people, the main way to increase the clothing insulation at low room temperature was to adapt to the risk of hypothermia (Kawashima et.al,1993; Bøkenes et.al,2009). Jiao's study also showed that in winter and summer, the effect of adjusting the thermal adaptation behavior of clothing on improving thermal comfort of the elderly was not obvious(Jiao et.al,2017).The results advocated that the elderly should make full use of measures to improve the thermal environment, such as by adjusting the level of activity rather than just increase or decrease clothing to improve thermal comfort, at the same time we need to have a better understanding to the harm of the environment to their own health.

Studies (Schellen et al.,2009, 2010) showed that elderly people have lower skin and core temperature than younger people. (Lu and Wang et al.,2015) pointed out that the thermal insulation of clothing that does not meet the needs of body will lead to reduction of core temperature and hypothermia. However, the existing researches on the thermal adaptation of clothing for the elderly mainly include the regularity of change of clothing insulation with indoor and outdoor temperature, as well as the relationship between clothing insulation and thermal sensation of the elderly (Yang et al.,2016; Jiao et.al,2017). In order to study the moderating effect of clothing insulation on the relationship between the elderly physiological parameters and environmental temperature, a comprehensive field study had been conducted in 19 elderly facilities with 1040 subjects aged 70 and above involved from January 2014 to April 2017 in Shanghai, China.

Methods

Nineteen elderly facilities in Shanghai were randomly selected for the field study. Research was conducted in a free-running thermal environment. There was a total of 355 males elderly people and 685 females elderly people. This research adopted objective physical environment measurements of indoor environments as well as physiological parameters of the elderly people and employed a subjective questionnaire survey to gather responses. Instruments were utilized to measure indoor air temperature(t_a), relative humidity(RH), air speed (V_a), and black-globe temperature(t_g). The evaluation process of the indoor thermal environment was based on the ASHRAE 55-2013 (ASHRAE 55, 2013) and GB 50785-2012 (GB/T 50785, 2012) standards. Operative temperature (t_{op}) was calculated from indoor air temperature and mean radiant temperature (t_r). UBK MEC-1000 portable multi-parameter monitor was adopted for the survey to measure finger skin temperature (T_s), heart rate(HR), systolic pressure(SBP), diastolic pressure(DBP), and oxyhemoglobin saturation(SpO_2) of the surveyed elderly people. Each subject collected 10 groups of data for each physiological parameter.

Total of 1040 valid questionnaires were obtained, of which 342 were obtained in winter, 330 were obtained in summer and 368 obtained in mid-season. In the survey, the garments and chairs of the elderly in the investigation were recorded by site observation and inquisition, and the insulation of these garments and

chairs was estimated from data presented in Tables from GB/T 50785-2012, ISO7730 (EN, ISO7730, 2005) and ASHRAE Standard 55–2013. (McCullough et al.,1985) pointed out that the insulation provided by an ensemble will be less than the sum of the component garments' clo values and predicted ensemble insulation from the sum of component garments' clo values. In this study, McCullough's formula is used to estimate clothing insulation.

$$I_{cl} = 0.676 \sum I_{cl,i} + 0.117 \quad (1)$$

Where $I_{cl,i}$ means i-th single garment's insulation, and I_{cl} means ensemble insulation.

Chair insulation was also added because the subjects were all seated.

Figure 1. The change of the operative temperature and the clothing insulation.

Pearson correlation coefficient was adopted to measure the correlation of the physiological parameters with the indoor operating temperature and the clothing insulation of the elderly people in four seasons. The results of the correlation analysis are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Correlations of physiological parameters and operative temperature, clothing insulation.

Variables		Spring		Summer		Autumn		Winter	
		t_{op}	I_{cl}	t_{op}	I_{cl}	t_{op}	I_{cl}	t_{op}	I_{cl}
Finger skin temperature (T_s)	C	0.386**	-0.108	0.414**	-0.037	0.680**	-	0.343**	-0.105
	P	0.000	0.242	0.000	0.502	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.052
Heart rate (HR)	C	-0.145	0.009	0.150**	-0.050	-0.152*	0.044	0.049	0.056
	P	0.115	0.921	0.006	0.367	0.017	0.490	0.371	0.299
Systolic pressure (SBP)	C	-0.152	0.091	-0.074	-0.035	-0.088	0.104	-0.042	-0.006
	P	0.100	0.326	0.180	0.529	0.166	0.103	0.444	0.917
Diastolic pressure (DBP)	C	-0.187*	0.067	-0.014	-0.027	-0.109	0.037	-0.073	-0.011
	P	0.041	0.471	0.803	0.629	0.087	0.562	0.179	0.842
Oxyhemoglobin saturation(SpO_2)	C	-0.158	0.159	-0.005	0.083	-0.055	0.117	-0.112*	0.033
	P	0.085	0.084	0.924	0.133	0.390	0.067	0.038	0.549

Note: * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

C– Pearson correlation coefficient; P – Significant level (2-sided); t_{op} – Operative temperature(°C); I_{cl} – Clothing insulation.

In this study, according to the test method proposed by (Baron and Kenny ,1986), if the interaction term of independent variable X (operative temperature) and moderator variable M (clothing insulation) can predict dependent variable Y (finger skin temperature), then there exists the moderating effect. This paper tested the moderating effect of clothing insulation on the relationship between finger skin temperature of the elderly people and operative temperature by means of hierarchical moderator regression. Test procedures: 1. Centralize variable; 2. Construct Product-Term; 3. Respectively put the dependent variable, the independent variable and the Product-Term of the independent variable and moderator variable into the hierarchical regression equation. 4. Results of hierarchical regression analysis show that if the Product-Term regression coefficient or the decision coefficient of hierarchical regression model significantly increases, then the moderating effect is significant. The analysis results are listed in table 2. The models in the table are expressed as:

$$M1: Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 M$$

$$M2: Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 M + \beta_3 XM$$

Where Y means finger skin temperature, X means operative temperature, M means clothing insulation.

Table 2. Moderating effect of clothing insulation on the relationship between finger skin temperature of the elderly people and operative temperature.

Explanatory variable	Finger skin temperature (T_s)							
	Spring		Summer		Autumn		Winter	
	M1	M2	M1	M2	M1	M2	M1	M2
Operative temperature (t_{op})	0.001**	0.003**	0.000**	0.001**	0.014**	0.014**	0.001**	0.007**
Clothing insulation (I_{cl})	0.912	0.732	0.149	0.362	0.053	0.072	0.925	0.966
$I_{cl} \times t_{op}$	-	0.387	-	0.926	-	0.608	-	0.816
R^2	0.641	0.665	0.928	0.928	0.946	0.947	0.577	0.578
F	10.701	0.812	45.300	0.009	158.996	0.274	10.909	0.056
Adjusted R^2	0.581	0.574	0.908	0.893	0.940	0.940	0.524	0.494
ΔR^2	0.002**	0.387	0.000**	0.926	0.000**	0.608	0.001**	0.816

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). M1 – Model 1; M2 – Model 2.

Figure 2. Fitting models of finger skin temperature and clothing insulation, operative temperature

Conclusions

1. The clothing insulation of the elderly had seasonal differences in Shanghai.
2. In autumn, the clothing insulation of the elderly was significantly negatively correlated with finger skin temperature.
3. Moderating effect of clothing insulation on the relationship between physiological parameters of the elderly people and environmental temperature was not significantly.
4. Fitting models were established to quantify the relationships between finger skin temperature and clothing insulation of the elderly as well as finger skin temperature and operative temperature.

References

- [1] Gagge, A. P., Winslow, C. E., & Herrington, L. P. (1938). The influence of clothing on the physiological reactions of the human body to varying environmental temperatures. *American Journal of Physiology-Legacy Content*, 124(1), 30-50.
- [2] Donaldson, G. C., Rintamäki, H., & Näyhä, S. (2001). Outdoor clothing: its relationship to geography, climate, behaviour and cold-related mortality in Europe. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 45(1), 45-51.
- [3] Havenith, G., Holmér, I., & Parsons, K. (2002). Personal factors in thermal comfort assessment: clothing properties and metabolic heat production. *Energy and buildings*, 34(6), 581-591.
- [4] Li, Y., Alshaer, H., & Fernie, G. (2009). Blood pressure and thermal responses to repeated whole body cold exposure: effect of winter clothing. *European journal of applied physiology*, 107(6), 673.
- [5] Marszałek, A., Bartkowiak, G., & Dąbrowska, A. (2018). Assessment of the effectiveness of modular clothing protecting against the cold based on physiological tests. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 1-12.
- [6] Cena, K.M., Spotila, J.R., Avery, H.W., 1986. Thermal comfort of the elderly is affected by clothes, activity and psychological adjustment. *ASHRAE Trans.* 92, 329–342.
- [7] Hwang, R.L., Chen, C.P., 2010. Field study on behaviors and adaptation of elderly people and their thermal comfort requirements in residential environments. *Indoor Air*. 20, 235–245.

- [8] Kawashima, Y., Tochiwara, Y., Gotoh, S., Uryu, Y., Ohmori, M., Masuda, Y., ... & Ohnaka, T. (1993). A study on body temperature regulation and residential thermal environments of the elderly—I. whole country survey of residential thermal environment and evaluation methods: RTE-index. *Journal of Thermal Biology*, 18(5-6), 487-499.
- [9] Bøkenes, L., Mercer, J. B., MacEvilly, S., Andrews, J. F., & Bolle, R. (2009). Annual variations in indoor climate in the homes of elderly persons living in Dublin, Ireland and Tromsø, Norway. *The European Journal of Public Health*, 21(4), 526-531.
- [10] Jiao, Y., Yu, H., Wang, T., An, Y., & Yu, Y. (2017). Thermal comfort and adaptation of the elderly in free-running environments in Shanghai, China. *Building and Environment*, 118, 259-272.
- [11] Schellen, L., van Marken Lichtenbelt, W., Loomans, M. G. L. C., Frijns, A., Toftum, J., & de Wit, M. (2009, September). Thermal comfort, physiological responses and performance of elderly during exposure to a moderate temperature drift. In *Proceedings of the 9th international conference and exhibition healthy buildings* (pp. 13-17).
- [12] Schellen, L., van Marken Lichtenbelt, W. D., Loomans, M. G. L. C., Toftum, J., & De Wit, M. H. (2010). Differences between young adults and elderly in thermal comfort, productivity, and thermal physiology in response to a moderate temperature drift and a steady-state condition. *Indoor air*, 20(4), 273-283.
- [13] Lu, Y., Wang, F., Wan, X., Song, G., Shi, W., & Zhang, C. (2015). Clothing resultant thermal insulation determined on a movable thermal manikin. Part I: effects of wind and body movement on total insulation. *International journal of biometeorology*, 59(10), 1475-1486.
- [14] Yang, J., Nam, I., & Sohn, J. R. (2016). The influence of seasonal characteristics in elderly thermal comfort in Korea. *Energy and Buildings*, 128, 583-591.
- [15] Jiao, Y., Yu, H., Wang, T., An, Y., & Yu, Y. (2017). The relationship between thermal environments and clothing insulation for elderly individuals in Shanghai, China. *Journal of thermal biology*, 70, 28-36.
- [16] GB/T 50785 (2012). Evaluation standard for indoor thermal environment in civil buildings. Beijing [in Chinese].
- [17] ISO 7730 (2005) Ergonomics of the Thermal Environment: Analytical Determination and Interpretation of Thermal Comfort Using Calculation of the PMV and PPD Indices and Local Thermal Comfort Criteria. Geneva: International Organization for Standardization.
- [18] ASHRAE. ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55-2013(2013). Thermal environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy. American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers, Atlanta.
- [19] McCullough, E. A., Jones, B. W., & Huck, J. (1985). A comprehensive data base for estimating clothing insulation. *Ashrae Trans*, 91, 29-47.
- [20] Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 51(6), 1173.